

Pushtimarg (The Path of Grace) in the UK and Gujarat

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Vaishnavism, Bhakti

Pushtimarg was developed by Vallabhacharya (1479–1531 CE), a Vedic philosopher who emphasised the Bhagavad Purana (a religious text of Hinduism). As a form of North Indian bhakti (devotion), the sampradaya follows Krishna as Shrinathji (as well as his other forms though focus is on his childhood). Vallabhacharya did not preach a life of asceticism or renunciation. His monistic philosophy was called Shuddhadvaita (pure non-dualism) where the focus is on the Supreme Being as personal, with the potential of developing a relationship. The Pushtimarg is a householder sampradaya (community) and therefore generating wealth and having a family are important parts of Krishna's world that he created for his lila (play). Historically, the popularity of the bhakti movement in India was twofold; "One the one hand, bhakti bypassed the hierarchy and ritualism of the Vedic sacrifices, monopolised by Brahmins and sponsored by their wealthy twice-born patrons, by teaching that salvation was open to all, regardless of caste, wealth, or sex, through the sincere and spontaneous expression of love for the divine. On the other hand, bhakti provided a more practicable alternative to the disciplined path followed by the renouncer" (Bennett 1993; 2). The community is dispersed globally, from Mozambique to Australia. In the 1990s, Pushtimarg gurus (who are called goswamis and are descendants of Vallabhacharya) began to travel more frequently to the diasporas around the US and Europe though this trend came relatively late compared to other forms of North Indian Krishna worship (e.g. Hare Krishna or ISKCON and the Swaminarayan faith).

Date Range: 1990 CE - 2020 CE

Region: Gujarat & the United Kingdom

Region tags: South Asia, Northern Britain, Scotland, England, India, Western India, Northern Ireland, Wales, Gujarat

The polygon in South Asia represents the area of Gujarat, while the polygon in Europe represents the region of the United Kingdom. Thus, this map represents the homeland and the diaspora.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: The Path of Grace: Social Organization and Temple Worship in a Vaishnava Sect. By Peter Bennett. Delhi: Hindustan Publishing Corporation, 1993
- Source 2: E. Allen Richardson. Seeing Krishna in America: The Hindu Bhakti Tradition of Vallabhacharya in India and Its Movement to the West. Jefferson: McFarland, 2014
- Source 3: Emilia Bachrach In the Service of Krishna Illustrated Narratives of Eighty-Four Vaishnavas from

a 1702 Manuscript in the Amit Ambalal Collection

- Source 1: Haberman, David L. (1993-08-01). "On Trial: The Love of the Sixteen Thousand Gopees". *History of Religions*. 33 (1): 44-70
- Source 2: Shadip Saha (2004), *Creating a Community of Grace: A History of the Pusti Marga in Northern and Western India (1493-1905)*, Doctoral Thesis
- Source 3: Dwyer, Rachel. "Caste, religion and sect in Gujarat: followers of Vallabhacharya and Swaminarayan." (1994): 165-190 in Ballard, Roger, and Marcus Banks. *Desh pardesh: the South Asian presence in Britain*. Hurst & Company, 1994.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://pushtimarg.net/>
- Source 1 Description: A Pushtimarg website run by a gurus family
- Source 2 URL: <http://www.pushti-marg.net/>
- Source 2 Description: A devotional website written by a devotee of Krishna
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.nathdwaratemple.org/>
- Source 3 Description: The official website of Nathdwara the home of Shreenatji

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: While contact with the group is pluralistic/accommodating in many regards, nonetheless, the Pushtimarg as a religious movement encourages Krishna worship and bhakti as the path to follow. Other 'margs' are acknowledged but the Vallabhacharya's path is considered the most important religious path. In the UK diaspora, it is difficult to determine who is and who isn't a Pushtimarg devotee. Membership is not tracked and people attend events and Havelis as Hindus in a wider sense as an ethnic and cultural community as well (see Dwyer 1994) It does depend in what ways pluralistic and accommodating are understood

Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: This depends on how neutral is understood. Other 'margs' are acknowledged but the

Pushtimarg is seen as the path to follow

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: While bhakti promotes an ideal-type egalitarian, casteless, genderless movement, caste distinction in varying degrees can be an issue in the context of Gujarat or within the Hindu community as a whole in the UK. This is not physically violent, however, has been argued as structural violence (Das 2007). Historically, Saha shows that despite being a casteless sect in membership terms, people would continue to live based on caste and class divisions (2004; 102). Currently, caste distinctions within the Pushtimarg mostly affect marriage matchmaking, if at all. Pushtimarg membership is more of a pre-requisite to marrying into a Pushtimarg family rather than caste.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: Pushtimarg is associated with family worship, therefore, some people are considered Pushtimarg from birth though there is an initiation that is the formal entry into the sampradaya

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: The initiation of brahma sambandh (attachment to god) is offered as choice. There is no dedicated time or age to take it. Individuals take the initiation for different reasons (family expectation, individual desire, marriage). It must be carried out by a guru of the Vallabhacarya lineage, therefore, often they are approached to do them or they offer set times during visits abroad where devotees can partake in the initiation.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Affiliation is through participation at all levels, from joining events, worshipping through seva (devotional service) at home to frequenting Havelis (Pushtimarg temples). However, there is a ritual that is a formal initiation into the sampradaya called brahma sambandh that can only happen through a Pushtimarg guru. The guru gives a devotee the 'Ashtakshar Mantra' (also known as Nam mantra - name mantra) i.e. 'Shri Krishna Sharanam Mama', said in your ear, three times. Devotees are then given two tulsi (holy basil seed) necklaces (also called a kanthi) as a signifier of faith. Devotees are then given the brahma sambandh mantra, symbolising a complete surrender of your entire being to Krishna

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: The Pushtimarg is not a proselytizing sampradaya by nature, though people encourage and offer formal membership to those already participating in public sphere worship. The aims of publicizing Pushtimarg events on television and online is to bring people to the sampradaya without actively proselytizing. Historically, Vallabhacarya and his son, Vitthalnath travelled around India and garnered a following through their recitations and discussions of scriptures during the 15th and 16th century.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: Historically, under Vallabhacarya's son's rule, Vitthalnath (also known as Gosainji), religious touring targeted patronage from Mughal officials (Saha 2004; 123) though this relationship was unstable throughout Mughal rule. Currently, in the UK the Pushtimarg is not supported as such by policy, but local councils and Pushtimarg Trusts work together on certain community projects and issues. In India, in the context of the pro-Hindu political party the Bharatiya Janata Party, there is support for all Hindu movements if sought.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: People can leave and come back through their personal choice, and if they move to another sampradaya, faith or none at all it is usually not a public abandonment.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Followers are not recorded nor is initiation recorded therefore numbers are potentially vast. Gurus are formed of divine lineage tracing back their roots to one of the seven sons of Vitthalnath (son of the founder of the Pushtimarg Vallabhacarya), and at present there are hundreds (perhaps more) of descendants. Each guru has the potential to develop a following. In terms of worship patterns, devotees can be Pushtimarg and worship publicly, but seva to Krishna is encouraged at home and is not 'monitored'. Krishna worship expands to other sampradayas so even having an image at home does not automatically signify affiliation

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (one of many small religious groups in sample region)

Notes: The Pushtimarg is difficult to narrowly define as a small or large religious group particularly because of the way people worship and ascribe membership. Other faiths who worship Krishna are allowed to participate in events and take darshan (sight of the divine) at Havelis without obstacles. Particularly in the diaspora, Havelis are filled with many 'small' Hindu groups that are not affiliated with the Pushtimarg and are non-members through initiation (See Richardson 2014, Footnote 76, 212)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

Notes: Pushtimarg gurus are all said to descend from Vallabhacarya, the founder of the sampradaya in the 16th century. Vallabhacarya had two sons, and after the eldest, Gopinathji, passed away, Vitthalnath (also known as Gosainji) became the official 'leader' who formed the more elaborate mode of seva practice that forms how it is practiced today. He had seven sons, who became the seven houses (gaddis) from which all Pushtimarg gurus descend from today.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

Notes: They do not have active powers in the sense of supernatural or can cause an effect on the world, rather, they are said to have inherited a special connection to the spiritual realm (alaukika) through being descended from Vallabhacarya.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– No

Notes: Normatively, no. They are born into their lineage traced back to Vallabhacarya and become leaders through this genealogy. However, devotees choose their guru

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– No

Notes: Normatively, no as gurus are hierarchically higher than devotees and related to Vallabhacarya. As humans who live in the current Kaliyuga (the Age of Darkness) they are fallible in that sense. There are historic cases of gurus being accused of scandals such as the Maharaj Libel Case in 1862 though since then, the sampradaya has distanced itself from these scandals

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Yes

Notes: It is not a direct yes or no. Devotees seek advice and counsel from gurus about the mundane and frequently act on that advice rather than obey unquestioningly. In terms of seva and the 'religious', devotees that seek advice do obey the guru as a spiritual authority

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The sampradaya (as with most in Hindu sampradayas) do not have a central text source or scripture. The Bhagavad Purana narrative of baby Krishna's many escapades is the main focus. There are also two hagiographical volumes called Chaurasi Vaishnavon ki Varta and the Dosau Bhavan Vaishnavon ki Varta. The former is the hagiography of the first eighty-four Pushtimarg devotees who followed Vallabhacarya, while the latter are the two-hundred and fifty-two of the followers of his son, Vittalnathji. In addition to these, is Vallabha's commentary on the Bhagavad called the Subodhini, Shodash Granth and Sri Sarvottam Stotra

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

Notes: Devotees who read the scriptures and absorb information from other sources of media have their own online forums, regular satsangs (religious forums) and websites to interpret the Pushtimarg literature and ways to perform seva

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Usually this is the guru lineage and Brahmins who have trained and studied the scriptures for their positions in the Haveli

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: The only place that could be considered a monumental religious structure would be the Shrinathji Mandir at Nathdwara. However, through the diaspora there is an increase in larger religious structures such as in the US, where Pushtimarg havelis are of a grander scale

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: Havelis are the traditional worship places for public worship. Haveli means 'mansion', and therefore, these are often structured to be houses. They are Krishna's house and often the guru's family home therefore they are less 'temple-like' and more 'house-like'. The only place that can be called a Mandir (temple) is Shrinathji in Nathdwara

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

- On persons
- At home
- All public spaces

Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Notes: In public Havelis there are swaroops or swarup ("Krishna's own (sva) form (rupa)" (Bennett 1993; 90) as opposed to murtis (as deities). This is usually a large swaroop of Shrinathji with a baby Krishna as a bronze swaroop in the front of him. Often you will see Swaminiji (Yamuna the goddess) and a statue of Vallabhacharya. Mount Govardhan can be present but usually outside or in a different space, where people do a parikrama (circumambulation). Chitrajis are painted pictures of Shrinathji and are also often present

Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Notes: People wear a kanthi (tulsi seed necklace) as a signifier of faith

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: Images or statues of Vallabhacarya are often present, but recall that he is said to have divine qualities, and some suggest he is descended from Radha. Images of the presiding gurus are also common on the walls.

↳ Other features of iconography:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: The whole of Braj in Utter Pradesh, India is of primary importance as the area that Krishna lived in during his lifetime. Gokul was his childhood home, Mathura was his birthplace and Vrandavan was where he passed much of his childhood. Mount Govardhan is of particular importance to the Pushtimarg as it is where Shreenathji (the avatar of Krishna) was revealed to Vallabhacarya (the founding saint). Devotees walk the mountain on foot (sometimes barefoot) on a parikrama (circumambulation) or prostrate fully on the ground and get up and continue this all around the mountain (dandavati).

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Notes: Pilgrimage (yatra) is not compulsory for devotees but many people go to Braj for yatras particularly if they live in India. Gurus will often host kathas (religious speaking events on Krishna) for seven or more days in Braj or at other sacred sites for huge audiences.

Vallabhacarya also travelled around India and the sites where he is said to have rested and spoken for seven days are called Baithaks. There are eighty-four in total. They are often marked by a small mound that is worshiped through adornments, food offerings, kirtans (religious songs) and seven daily darshan ('sight' of the sacred for the public opening) times. They do not always house images or iconography.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Not really yes or no. Vallabhacarya's philosophy is called Shuddhadvaita or Pure NonDualism. He disavowed the theory of the world as Maya (illusion), but rather all of the world is part of Krishna's wishes. Humans are part of Krishna but they do not realise it yet. Once a devotee realises this duality does not exist. The human-divine relationship is like sparks to a flame (see Bennett 1993 and Richardson 2014). The soul (jiva) does not have the same powers as the divine but is a small part of it.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: The jiva as the soul is connected as a small part to the divine (Brahma) but is not conscious of that until they have developed love for Krishna

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The Pushtimarg devotees do not believe in an afterlife for the individual consciousness. They return to Krishna, in unity with him, in his eternal lila (play). However, this is with the background of reincarnation theory where individuals are reborn in different bodies, until they perceive the world as devotees of Krishna

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– Yes [specify]: Goloka is Krishna's kingdom - a celestial home of the eternal lila. This is separate from Vaikuntha the kingdom of Vishnu

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form:

– Yes

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

Notes: It is possible - within the Pushtimarg karma is something that is spoken about and

acknowledged but not for the devotees who do seva.

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: Pushtimarg death rituals are the same as other Hindu death rituals through cremation and other Vedic rites. There are differences for the attendees where they cannot wear the kanti (tulsi seed necklace) they wore to a funeral again. Mala Pehramni is a ritual performed by a guru on the request of the family of the person who passes away. It involves changing a devotees kanti with new kantis blessed by a guru and providing them for other devotees if this ceremony is done at a Haveli

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

- ↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :
 - No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

- No

Are grave goods present:

- Yes

Notes: Not 'goods' per say. The body is given flowers, sometimes sandalwood or tumeric paste, and water is given to the persons mouth.

- ↳ Personal effects:

- Yes

Notes: Personal choice of clothing and adornments

- ↳ Valuable items:

- Yes

- ↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

- No

- ↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

- Yes

- ↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

- No

- ↳ Other grave goods:

- Yes

Are formal burials present:

- Yes

Notes: It depends what is meant by formal burials. The cremated body can be scattered as per the wishes of the family or deceased

- ↳ As cenotaphs:

- No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Ashes scattered as per individual or family wishes

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: There are supernatural beings present, primarily centred around Krishna. About 5000 years ago, Krishna is said to have come to earth, and begun his earthly play (lila) as an avatar of Vishnu. Though in the Pushtimarg, he is the supreme reality rather than Vishnu. Krishna's evil uncle Kamsa was the brother of Devaki, who is Krishna's birth mother. Kamsa was told by a prophecy that Devaki's eighth son would kill him for his sinful behaviour as the ruler of Mathura. Devaki and her husband, Vasudeva, were imprisoned and each of her children were killed as they were born. At the time of Krishna's birth, the entire prison was fortified by extra guards but at the time of birth only Vasudeva was awake as a divine sleep affected everyone else. Awestruck at the cosmic birth of Krishna, Vasudeva begs him to take on a more approachable appearance and so Krishna becomes darker skinned and a baby (Hawley 1992; 55). Vasudeva frees himself from his shackles and takes Krishna across the river to Gokul. During the monsoon Vasudeva is aided by a multi-headed snake to protect them from the rain. Giving Krishna to his friend, Nanda, Krishna is swapped for a baby girl that Nanda's wife, Yashoda, has given birth to. Shrinathji comes in the 15th century. He emerged from the Govardhanath the mountain in Braj, when the founder of the Pushtimarg, Shree Vallabhacarya, appeared to meet him. It must be noted that Shrinathji is a place, as well as an image of Krishna. There is a pilgrimage place called ShriNathji in Rajasthan where Shrinathji the swarup resides. In terms of the goddess, the Pushtimarg have Swaminiji. She envelopes the images of Yamunaji (the physical river, the goddess and the river goddess) and Radha, Krishna's divine consort (Vaudeville 1982) While Vallabhacarya is in human form, he is considered to have divine qualities. There are some devotees believe he is a divine incarnation of Krishna.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
 - No
 - Notes: Krishna can be said to represent features of the moon but is not seen as a 'sky deity'

- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No
 - Notes: Krishna was a king in his lifetime. Among other roles such as child, lover, friend, brother. Predominantly he is a god.

- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes

- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - Yes [specify]: Different kinship roles parallel to his life on earth

- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - Notes: Yes and no. Knowledge is not 'restricted' in any sense
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: All knowledge of this world as Krishna is the source and creator of the world

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: Through grace

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: Yes and no. Krishna does not actively punish people (see Sanford 2008)

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Yes

Notes: For specific food offerings and through seva, hunger is part of devotion

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Notes: Yes and no. In the seva of Krishna one can worship other beings, but this can lead to Anyashray (worshiping other gods/goddesses) and becoming detached from Krishna so is actively discouraged

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Human qualities as part of divine lila, as a child, king, warrior and lover

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: In bhakti in general there are instances of possession. However, this is not openly a part of the Pushtimarg who do not believe in spirit possession by Krishna. Some descriptions are better described as part of mystical experiences.

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Through sight (darshan)

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: All knowledge that Krishna shares with them

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: They can appear in different forms such as Yamuna as a river, a goddess, and a river goddess

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Notes: Divine beings appear as humans but are essentially divine so it depends how mixed human-divine beings are defined

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Swaminiji is often worshiped at Havelis. She is the goddess Yamuna (although interchanges with Radha, Krishna's divine consort)

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

Notes: Though they appear in a variety of kinship/familial roles in relation to Krishna

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: There are pan-Hindu social norms to be adhered to in the Pushtimarg. Monogamy and vegetarianism with other dietary restrictions (no onions, garlic or alcohol) are examples of this. Monitoring comes through other devotees, contexts and through spiritual authority of the Vallabhkhul (divine lineage of Vallabhacarya). Other social norms include ethical behaviour (no murder, lying or cheating for example) as well as coming together to help other Vaishnavas primarily. Hospitality is a part of community behaviour more widely, however, more orthodox members will not take food or drink from a person who has not been initiated into the Pushtimarg. It must be noted that Krishna is a god who does not follow social conventions and is all about breaking social norms to follow him in his devotion theologically (see Sanford 2008) These norms still exist for everyday life for devotees. Only once a devotee has reached ultimate absorption in the reality of Krishna, like a gopi from Braj who leaves her husband for Krishna lila (play), do social norms and conventions not apply.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: Vegetarianism and no onions or garlic

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: To an extent. Most of seva is based on bhava (mood or emotion) so some rituals are adapted once a relationship is developed with Krishna, seva becomes more personalised

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: Conversion in a flexible definition, in consideration to the marg people's jivas (souls) are destined to follow

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: In a sense. Where people should deserve what they get and use whatever they have in service of Krishna

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: Strict purity rules apply for the majority of people, though once a devotee reaches a certain level of relationship with Krishna, these too can be forgotten/forgone

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: General behaviour

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: In some ways. Bad things are not attributed to Krishna, only good things are because of his grace (krupa). Bad happenings are due to the human ego and faults. Devotees and gurus attribute 'punishments' retrospectively

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: As Krishna desires it could be understood as many supernatural beings

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: Possible

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The 'afterlife' punishment would be to be apart from Krishna and not be in his seva. Depending on how 'afterlife' is understood. The goal is to get back to Krishna, even if reincarnated

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: As punishments are understood as such after the fact, this is opposed to good things/rewards are understood as grace from Krishna

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

Notes: Possibly

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

Notes: Possibly

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

Notes: Possibly

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Notes: Possibly

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

Notes: Possibly

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Possibly

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Possibly

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: Possibly

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

Notes: Possibly

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: Possibly

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: Nothing good (within the Pushtimarg) happens without *krupa* or grace. Pushti also means grace which is why Pushtimarg translates to the path of grace. However, while people refer to themselves as *pushti* souls ('graced souls'), more commonly they used the word *krupa* for grace being given. Pushti souls are a part (*ansh*) of Krishna that have been separated from Krishna. Vallabhacarya's emphasis was that *seva* would allow souls to get back to Krishna. the spiritual Gatekeeper to Krishna is the divine manifestation of the Yamuna river, Yamunaji. She is the daughter of the Sun and the brother of Yama, the god of Death. Without Yamunaji's *krupa* you cannot reach Krishna in the first place. Yamunaji is considered the mother of all Pushti souls and leads her children to Krishna.

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Could be thought of as such, but ultimately through Krishna

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: Could be thought of as such, but ultimately through Krishna

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: Could be thought of as such

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: Could be thought of as such

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness[]:

– Yes

Notes: Could be thought of as such

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: In reference to unity with Krishna and more seva

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Notes: Afterlife meaning unity with Krishna as opposed to rebirth or reincarnation

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: As the only joy of seva (selfless devotional service) to Krishna is more seva, that is the only

reward devotees desire. Unity with Krishna is the ultimate reward

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: In many ways the reward is doing seva

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

Notes: Possibly

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

Notes: Possibly

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

Notes: Possibly peace in a wider sense and social stability, internal peace yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Notes: Possibly

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

Notes: Possibly

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: Possibly

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: Possibly

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

Notes: Possibly

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

Notes: Possibly

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: Possibly

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: The theology of the sampradaya would not acknowledge the role of a saviour as such. Historically, one could argue that Vallabhacharya could be considered a 'saviour' for the Pushtimarg souls that were 'lost'. His philosophy was for the people of the world to find all the pushti souls and bring them to Krishna again as a teacher. Some people consider him an incarnation of divine power. However, the messianic concept is not a common narrative.

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: It is a pan-Hindu belief that the last avatar of Vishnu, Kalki, will destroy the world and regenerate the universe. Though the Kali Age is described as terrible and fearful, there are positives described in the scriptures through bhakti worship shown by Veluthat, K. (2014). Worship of Krishna would make the Age of Kali 'good' because worship has immediate effects (Ibid). "In the age of Kali, O, listen, the intelligent ones worship the dark-hued, splendid, Krsna with all his entourage by means of sankīrtanayajñas....Hari, the Lord of Welfare, is worshipped in each age appropriate to it. The discerning ones, who know the essence [of things], always prefer the age of Kali when just by singing psalms all desired things can be earned, when ultimate peace is possible, and when the cycle of birth and death is destroyed..." In short, Visnu will protect all such as would worship at his feet" (Ibid; 176) As this world is all Krishna's play, transformation cannot be predicted or known about, rather devotees desire to continue to do seva and devote themselves to Krishna in the world as it is. However, the end of Kali Yuga marks the start of Satya Yuga (the Golden Age), beginning the cycle of the four yugas again.

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– No

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– Yes

Notes: At the end of Kaliyuga. Kaliyuga is said to have begun when Krishna left the world about 5000 years ago. The current Kaliyuga will last 432,000 years in total before the new Age of Satya Yuga begins (of righteousness and dharma) (for more see <http://www.krishna.com/info/kali-yuga> though this is written from the Hare Krishna Vaishnava movement it is the same for the Pushtimarg)

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

Notes: In a way. Some say that those dedicated to Krishna in seva will be absorbed in seva so much so that the effects of Kalki destroying the world does not affect them. Kalki will be born in order to destroy all the evils in the world, when it has become irreparable

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– Yes

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– Yes

Notes: Likely

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– Yes

Notes: Yes and no, sometimes this is contested. Seva to Krishna will continue but the New Age of Satya Yuga is seen as an age of piousness and righteousness so certain things may change

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There are norms prescribed by the Pushtimarg community as a whole. Seva is strongly encouraged as part of a healthy religious life. While doing seva is perceived as contingent on a persons' bhava (mood or devotional attitude) this can be part of established family practice rather than individual. Vegetarianism is required on taking initiation as well as no onions or garlic for more orthodox members of the group. Monogamy in marriage are important within the wider context as well as in the sampradaya. General ethical behaviour is prescribed by the sampradaya and devotees are guided by gurus, other devotees and the wider Hindu context. This includes norms such as causing no harm to people, lying, gambling or cheating and so on. Caring for cows and other animals is part of encouraged behaviour. Many people will keep a portion of food aside to serve to cows or other animals if they are nearby. Caring for other Vaishnavas is important, through feeding, communicating and participating in festivals or seva in Havelis.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: General social (or conventional) and moral norms are interchangeable and pan-Hindu for the most part and are not Pushtimarg specific. Life for many Pushtimarg devotees is centred on seva and the reality of Krishna as Supreme Being. Much of moral behaviour is dependent on how absorbed (or orthodox) a devotee is in seva. Krishna himself is not a role model of behaviour as such (as opposed to Rama, the avatar before him, representing dharma (duty) and responsibility) and was often said to have come as the avatar of joy and spontaneity in his lila (divine play). As above, society and context dictate the community's ideal behaviour.

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present (but not emphasized)

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals (any time period)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: While some of the below virtues are advocated by the sampradaya this is pan-Hindu rather than Pushtimarg specific. Many virtues are open to interpretation drawn from various stories of Krishna or the scriptures. These are discussed at length in kathas, satsangs and amongst devotees.

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

Notes: This is based on the Bhagavad Gita's representation of Krishna as a warrior. However, the Pushtimarg, while acknowledging this part of Krishna's life, worship him as a child. Therefore, this is not explicit or discussed in the Pushtimarg

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

Notes: There are four different types of bhava (mood) in devotional bhakti though all bhavas are often used interchangeably; dasya bhava (master-servant), vatsalya bhava (parent-child), sakhya bhava (friendship), madhurya bhava (lover-beloved). The most emphasised in the Pushtimarg is that of the parent, particularly that of a mother and this is important for seva

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

Notes: To an extent

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

Notes: To an extent. In fieldwork this was not institutionalised by every guru family. Rather, Trusts would organise charity drives based on local community needs and desires.

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

Notes: Selflessness is the primary tenet of doing seva for Krishna. However, this varies when it comes to human-human relationships. In the name of Krishna, selflessness is praised.

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

Notes: Certain sources of food and cleanliness during religious acts are important

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

Notes: To an extent. Respectfulness shows a calm and peaceful demeanor, which seva should inspire for the mundane world

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

Notes: For the individual self, yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

Notes: To an extent

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– Yes

Notes: This is not actively discouraged or encouraged for the individual. Again, if there power or status, if it is in the service of Krishna it would be praised

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

Notes: Bhakti is a devotional movement and the bhavas are devotional moods which are developed in order to get closer to Krishna

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

Notes: To an extent. Emotional attachment is held more important than knowledge (jnana)

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

Notes: To an extent. Emotional attachment is held more important than knowledge

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– Yes

Notes: Appreciating beauty as the world was created by Krishna so in essence devotees are encouraged to appreciate the beauty of his lila

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: Vegetarianism

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual

abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: Couples are encouraged to have children and be monogamous. In another note on worship, vatsalya bhava (the mood of a parent-child) is the ideal devotional mood for the Pushtimarg (See Peter Bennett 1993; E. Allen Richardson 2014). While madhurya bhava (that of a lover) is present, this is more developed in the Gaudiya philosophy of worship. Passionate love is not discouraged if it is Krishna-centred, though again this is more associated with Chaitanya's teachings in the Gaudiya tradition. Rasa (taste or essence) theory is an aesthetic devotional emotion related to much of the poetry and performances in Braj on Krishna worship. Rasa as an emotion involves a complex full experience of the divine. See Owen Lynch 1990 for more details.

Monogamy (males):

– Yes

Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: Pro-creation as primary purpose

Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: Pro-creation as primary purpose

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Fasting for the Brahma Sambandh initiation ritual is required for the day before. While it is not obligatory many people do fast for certain occasions. The most common is for Ekadashi. This is every 11th Tithi (day) in the Hindu calendar based on the lunar cycle. There are two Ekadashi fasting in a month, about every two calendar weeks. The idea behind fasting is to bring people closer to Krishna, and leave their own needs aside for the desires of Krishna.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Vegetarianism, no onions or garlic, and no alcohol are common food taboos in the Pushtimarg. In the diaspora and in India (mostly outside of Gujarat which is a vegetarian state), many casual

participants do not strictly follow these taboos when not performing worship acts. However, if they become more orthodox and are frequent participants, they do follow them. Havelis are strict in their food offerings to Krishna and follow the dietary restrictions at all times. Sattvic, Rajas and Tamas are the three gunas (qualities) that are part of the reason. Sattvic foods are clean, pure and calming, while Rajas is restless and can lead to anger, and Tamas is lethargic. The latter two are not necessarily 'bad' but do not promote a focus on Krishna devotion. Therefore, Tamas and Rajas relates to individual ego and desires over Krishna worship.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: The Pushtimarg is a householder sampradaya as long as it is all dedicated to Krishna and worship of him, wealth can be sought.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Seva is most often translated as 'selfless service' which is a daily devotion towards an image of baby Krishna with ritual parallels to human behaviours, such as feeding, bathing, and singing to the deity. Seva is different for everyone, and therefore, there is no set time for it. Seva to Krishna is done at

home and darshan is done at the Haveli (temple). Though seva can be done in the Haveli, it is usually helping the priests (mukhijas) with food preparation, flower garland making, singing kirtans (religious songs) and other public forms of seva. In the Haveli there are seven darshans and these are mostly paralleled at home in different forms. 6:30: Mangla darshan. This is when Krishna is woken up with kirtans, and given breakfast, before darshan opens so as not to scare the young child with huge crowds of people. Aarti (ritual waving of a flame) is performed at this time by the priest. 9am: Shringar darshan. This is when Krishna is dressed up and shown a mirror to check he is happy with what he is wearing. Before his 'play time' he is given a snack of dry fruits. 9:45- 10:30 Gwal darshan. This is when Krishna is taking his cows to pasture and playing with his cowherd friends. 10:45: Ragbhog darshan. This is the main meal of the day for Krishna with aarti performed by the head of the guru family. After this darshan there is a period of rest called Anavasara where Krishna naps. At 4:15 is Uthapan darshan when Krishna is woken up from his nap with a conch shell to go back and play again. There are two other darshans between this that are closed: Bhog where a meal is served to Krishna and Aarti when Krishna is coming back from playing with his cowherd friends. The final darshan of the day is Shayan at 6:45pm where Krishna is being prepared for bedtime by changing his clothes. He is given light snacks now as well. There are three basic tenets to seva, rag, (music) bhog (food) and shringar (adornments). For rag and shringar, much is left to the skills and choices of the individual devotee (attributed to Krishna's desires being expressed in various ways to them), however, bhog has a some structure in the sense that gurus often advise people how to do it in stages from offering a simple sugar sweet (misri) to a full meal.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: Similarly to virtues and moral norms, membership requires vegetarianism, avoiding alcohol and gambling.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Notes: Yes and no. Marginalisation happens naturally when people become more and more involved in personal seva and the Haveli, as the time spent increases as people become more attached

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 3

Notes: Because timings vary considerably it is not easy to say. Darshan times are not obligatory to attend but they happen in the Haveli everyday. At home these vary according to the stage of seva one is at, or how long devotees can dedicate to seva

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: While they are not requirements and many orthodox devotees do not attend as they are involved in their personal seva, the Pushtimarg is well-known for its festivals and feasts (see Toomey). For more details on Festivals see <https://pushtimarg.net/festivals/>

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There can be thousands. It varies by context. It also depends on the guru and his personal following to how many people the guru can attract to their events. In Nathdwara during festival season, tens of thousands of people come for darshan of Shreenathji, but there are too many to estimate and not all will be part of the Pushtimarg.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It depends. It varies by context, event type and guru. Events do not always follow darshan patterns, though these will continue throughout an event in the Haveli.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Through the guru and priests (mukhiyas) at public events

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: It depends on the context.

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– No

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

Notes: Vegetarianism, no onions or garlic and no alcohol. Indian food is offered in rites and festivals.

↳ Hair:

– No

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: Traditional Indian wear is prescribed. For women it is sarees or traditional Indian (for more orthodox people this includes no pins or hairclips, bra or nail polish etc.) and for men it is a dhoti (a male sarong) and wrap top (bandi).

↳ Ornaments:

– No

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

Notes: If we consider Braj Basha as archaic (the language of Braj). It is spoken intermingled with other Indian languages depending on the region (most commonly Gujarati and Hindi) or English as well in the UK. Braj Basha is known for being poetic (<https://www.britannica.com/topic/Braj-Bhasha-language>) and related to Krishna worship

↳ Other:

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Notes: Gujarati terms of sister (ben) and brother (bhai) are used for all members of the community, whether Pushtimarg or not. In Pushtimarg, people can often call women sakhi (friend) or men (sakha though this is more rare), but most people will employ bhai or ben for each other. In terms of the divine, devotees will call Krishna their friend, child, lover and master. This is related to their bhavas (devotional moods). There are four different types of bhava in devotional bhakti though all bhavas are often used interchangeably; dasya bhava (master-servant), vatsalya bhava (parent-child), sakhya bhava (friendship), madhurya bhava (lover-beloved)

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: This is a sampradaya, which is often translated as a sect, and is closer to a religious movement or tradition.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: By providing opportunities for seva within Havelis, many retired/older men and women who go to make garlands or perform other types of seva find a community group through the Haveli. Satsangs (religious forums), events and daily darshan also provide a similar community support system. This is not an outreach programme but rather an effect of Haveli public seva opportunities

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: Formal religious education is for children in a pathshala (a religious school for children) that only runs once a week at most. Each Haveli or group decides how, whether and when to do this and it is not compulsory. Satsangs and kathas are organised by the Havelis or devotees themselves to provide a space for religious education and interpretation. These are increasingly becoming more formal through the Haveli in the diasporas, including some forms of Gujarati/Hindi language lessons though this is at its infancy in terms of education.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: International and Indian Havelis are run through a Trust. A guru from the divine lineage is a spiritual leader of the Haveli but day to day are run by Trustees chosen by the guru or the community.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: There are donation systems in place called Manoraths (meaning desires). Manoraths are also acts of seva that devotees perform for the desire of Krishna for example, decorating Krishna's area with a certain flower. This is not a tax or tithe that is levied on devotees. Rather it is a choice of the individual to do so. Certain donations are more forcefully encouraged (not forced by the institution), for instance, dropping a pound coin into the donation box at the Haveli or giving some money to the guru when he is present, but these are not equated to tax or tithe for members of the Pushtimarg. The donation systems are for various seva carried out in Havelis throughout the day similar to a sponsorship. A person or family can sponsor Ragbhog, Krishna's afternoon lunch for instance, and get a portion of the food for prasad (blessed food). Wealthier families also can sponsor whole events like kathas (religious speaking events), supporting thousands of people for food and paying for the guru's accommodation, family and other devotees around them to join.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The state and country they live in

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: Possibly. It is context and country dependent

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: Possibly

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Notes: It is context dependent

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Notes: It is context dependent

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: It is context and country dependent

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The state and country they live in

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: It is context and country dependent

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: While scriptures are written Sanskrit this is not Pushtimarg specific. The Pushtimarg use poetry and other literature written in Braj Basha which is spoken throughout Braj in Utter Pradesh is used by the local population and the religious group. The sampradaya use regional languages depending on

their context as well.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Braj Basha which is spoken throughout Braj in Utter Pradesh is used by the local population and the religious group, as well as regional languages

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Braj Basha

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: People follow the Hindu lunar calendar

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: It varies on context. In general in the UK it would be a no. In Gujarati it would depend on whether the devotee or the Haveli have small scale farms attached. Often they have dairy cows for ghee, milk and yoghurt.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Pushtimarg (The Path of Grace) in the UK and Gujarat, Das, Veena, Veena Das, Arthur Kleinman, Mamphela Ramphele, and Pamela Reynolds. *Violence and Subjectivity*. University of California Press, 2000. https://books.google.com/books/about/Violence_and_Subjectivity.html?hl=&id=7KsEcQnb2VIC.

Reference: Pushtimarg (The Path of Grace) in the UK and Gujarat, Sanford, A. Whitney. *Singing Krishna*. SUNY Press, 2009. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=sBTR69xVpEAC>.

Reference: Pushtimarg (The Path of Grace) in the UK and Gujarat, Lynch, Owen M.. *Divine Passions*. University of California Press, 1990. https://books.google.com/books/about/Divine_Passions.html?hl=&id=y3HEvGsKflwC.

Reference: Pushtimarg (The Path of Grace) in the UK and Gujarat, Toomey, Paul. *Food from the Mouth of Krishna Feasts and Festivals*. Hindustan Publishing Corporation, 1994. https://books.google.co.uk/books/about/Food_from_the_Mouth_of_Krishna.html?id=GzTXAAAAMAAJ&redir_esc=y.

Reference: Pushtimarg (The Path of Grace) in the UK and Gujarat, Veluthat, Kesavan. "Making the Best of a Bad Bargain: The Brighter Side of Kaliyuga.". *Indian Historical Review* 41, no. 2 (December 1, 2014): 173–84. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0376983614544571>.